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Pardoning A Heartless Mother: My Story of Embracing Forgiveness and Vengefulness

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I believe that home ought to be referred as a place that offers safety, warmth, and solace. However, my mother was a violent, controlling, and abusive woman, and I was always afraid of her. I feel like I have to suffer from an abusive mother as it would help me to develop into the person I am today. No matter what the circumstance is, I always tell myself that I am human. I have to deal with this, and hope one day can have that "get out of jail free card" in life. Forgiveness does not require much time. Dealing with your sentiments or processing your emotions could take some time. But all it takes to forgive is a choice.

It was on the twilight of the sixth of November (*my birthday*) when I asked permission to my mother to rub shoulders with my friends since I know that my birthday would be lonely and sad at home subsequent to no one's preparing for it except them (*my friends*). I have always been blessed with good friends in my whole life. It hurts to notice that nobody in my family really cares enough to remember my birthday. ALWAYS. That is why I am very grateful to have this circle of friends. Despite of having heartless and strict mother, I've decided to go to my friends who've prepared a lot for my birthday. She got pretty upset. That was the time she kicked, beat, and cursed at me. Well, I know I am used to it but please not just on my birthday. It was only the two of us. I cried out for help as my mother shut the door. Nobody came to rescue me. As I attempted to escape, my mother kept kicking me and hitting my head. However, she stopped me and kept beating me in all over my body. She hits me extremely hard. I tried to shield my face, scream, and cry, but I was unable to remain upright. Next, I stumbled and fell. She cursed me, opened the door, and left me right away. I felt alone and hopeless at the time, and I wanted to die. My face and knees were bleeding. There was a time I questioned God because of the things happening in my life. Everything took place on my birthday. I left home at that moment. I spent two (2) months staying at the residence of my closest friend. My birthday is permanently inked on my right arm since it holds special meaning for me. That was the first time that I wasn't able to celebrate my Christmas and New Year together with my so called 'family'. My heart was suddenly filled with wrath and hatred for them. I was traumatized by the experience because of that abuse. It hurt so bad. As time passed, I was filled with hate, anger, and vengeance toward them. until I met a kind, compassionate, and understanding colleague. She taught me through the bible the love of God, His mercies, His love and His forgiveness. Then it struck on me that if God had pardoned me of all my transgressions, then I must also learn to pardon my mother.

I've now managed to forgive and show compassion for my mother after years of struggle and unrelenting agony in my eyes. I firmly think that forgiveness heals families, has

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revitalized my spirit, restored my soul, granted me the serenity I deserve, and has blessed my biological mother as well. Some things aren't meant to last forever. And although this person (*my mother*), I could never bring myself to say to them that I regret having her as my mom. Because I don't. If I were given a chance to choose another mother, I would still choose my mom because I still owe her a lot. I will always choose to forgive and wish her well, regardless of what she decides to do—to choose forgiveness or resentment. If not, I would be trapped by unfavorable feelings and ideas and constrained by answers to questions that I might never receive.

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